

Fault detection of CRFP during initial loading

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SUMMARY: This paper addresses the application of three kinds of testing methods with the purpose of finding defective items in the manufacturing of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) prosthetic feet. None of the methods used applies more than initial loading of the specimens in order to collect data. The three methods are based on the following: Acoustic Emission (AE) signals, natural frequency response and stiffness measurements. Some of the specimens used in the testing were intentionally made with flaws; and the aim of the project is to recognize those. The AE signal analyzing proves to be the most promising approach, showing prominent activity during parameter analysis in the case of delaminated specimens. Comparison to fatigue testing supports our findings in that particular analysis.

KEYWORDS: Acoustic emission, Stiffness, Natural frequencies, Initial loading.

INTRODUCTION

By analyzing three different kinds of signals obtained from either the initial loading of a prosthetic foot (AE signal and stiffness curve) or impulse loading (natural frequency response), the aim of the project is to find a method to indicate the quality of a carbon fiber object and eliminate the need for further testing. This would also make it possible to test every object produced in a quick and easy way instead of randomly selecting objects to test and thereby risk that the untested ones are defect free. By testing every object, the quality of sold products could be enhanced.

The specimens tested in this research are of a certain type and size of a prosthetic foot from the prosthetic manufacturer Össur¹, namely a VARI-FLEX, size 26 (Fig. 1). The stiffness category was supposed to be the same for all specimens, around 5, but as it turned out the specimens ranged from 4-6 which equals 1045-1412 N at 47.3 mm bending in a stiffness test. The design of the foot is thinnest at the toe and thickens as it gets closer to the ankle.

Fig. 1: A fully assembled prosthetic foot of the type discussed here.

¹ www.ossur.com

Various factors influence the quality of a finished CRFP product; storage conditions, time in storage, curing conditions. The final finishing of the product, such as drilling and grinding, also has an impact on the quality.

The full product was not used for testing; assembled it consists of a split toe and a two part heel. When stiffness testing, the parts are tested separately; but we only focus on the toe in this study, which is constructed out of carbon fiber prepregs. The outermost layers consist of four layers of woven carbon/epoxy prepregs laid at 45°. Between the outer layers unidirectional carbon/epoxy prepreg tapes are laid at 0°. The length of the unidirectional tape varies in order to produce the required change in thickness along the foot. An exception is the area around the holes where extra unidirectional carbon/epoxy prepreg tapes are laid at 90° for added strength.

The current testing process at Össur involves, along with visual inspection, stiffness testing a certain number of prosthetic feet from each finished panel of feet containing eight units. Fatigue testing is also performed for some assembled prosthetics according to the ISO 10328 specifications in an ISO 10328 Foot/Limb test machine² at Össur's testing facilities. In the test, a foot is flexed 2,000,000 times. The time to complete one test can vary between 8-23 days. When fatigue is tested in this project, however, the test is accelerated by increasing the peak-to-peak load amplitude by 60%. The best feet endure around 200,000 cycles, or 10 times fewer cycles than norm.

The remainder of the article is as follows. After an introduction to the background on the different methods utilized, the testing procedure and equipment used is described. In the section Post-Processing and Results, the analysis of each method and its outcome is discussed. Finally, conclusions are drawn from the results presented.

BACKGROUND

Over the past several decades, the use of carbon fiber composites has increased along with progress in its manufacturing. The fields of carbon fiber applications seem limitless when it comes to utilizing the appealing characteristics of these materials, such as their extraordinary strength to weight ratio.

Instruments made out of carbon fiber composites are often laminated; such that carbon fiber sheets are put on top of each other with thin layers of the base material, or matrix, in between. Carbon fiber sheets are produced in several different ways. The directions of highest strength in the carbon fiber sheets depend on the alignment of individual fibers [1], [2].

Common defects seen in carbon fiber composites include matrix cracking, fiber breakage, fiber-matrix debonding and delamination between plies. The last one, delamination, is the most serious. Damage can form under relatively low strain if the production has been faultily manufactured, and can quickly become more serious [3]. If the matrix, for example, is prone to cracking, it often leads to delamination later on. When load is applied on the material, damages increase and the mechanical properties deteriorate, causing the material to fail [4], [5]. The behavior of a carbon fiber composite is mainly dependant on how crack resistant the matrix is, the strength of the connections between the matrix and fibers and the composite layer adhesiveness [6].

Damage detection methods based on natural frequency analysis are among the oldest and most often used in the field as it can be used on virtually any object. The inducement of vibration can be of variable kinds as can the recording of responses. Changes in natural frequencies can be linked directly to stiffness changes. Another major benefit is that natural frequency analysis is a non-destructive testing (NDT) form. On the other hand, it is difficult to find small damages or position specific local ones, except when many sensors are used

² www.enduratec.com

along with comparisons to numerical models. Since natural frequencies are very densely packed at higher frequencies, the main use is made of frequencies up to a few kHz [7], [8], [9]. If damages have already occurred in the material, for example delamination, the reduction in natural frequencies depends on the dimension and positioning of the damage. The largest change is seen in frequencies that have similar wavelengths to the dimension of damage. Therefore, large damages that induce an overall stiffness reduction can be seen at lower frequencies, whereas changes in higher frequencies point to small, localized damages that have not yet managed to affect the object as a whole. This behavior of the natural frequencies results from the stress field in a vibrating object differing along with the wave mode being induced. The effect of damage on natural frequencies is therefore a combination of the position/size of damage and the stress field. At higher frequencies the stress field has become more uniform across the object; if two damages of the same kind but with different positions are checked, the effects on natural frequencies are very similar [3], [9].

Methods based on Acoustic Emission (AE) are among only a few NDT methods that have been shown capable of recognizing all of the four main damage groups in carbon fiber composites. The technique is named after the sound energy released as micro structural changes occur in materials. If the energy is sufficient the material emits sounds that are obtainable with adequate measurement equipment. The waves from the source spread through the material and reach the surface where they cause small displacements that can be picked up with a piezoelectric sensor. The signal obtained is then analyzed. The signals are highly dependant on the testing equipment used as well as the object being tested. These methods differ from other NDT methods as damages can be noticed at the time they occur.

AE signals can be divided into two groups; continuous emission and burst emission. The continuous signals are low energy and are influenced by the load size that the materials are subjected to; individual peaks can not be distinguished from each other. This type of emission is usually related to movement and resistance inside the material. Burst emission has a much larger amplitude and energy and in this type of signal, individual peaks can be recognized. High-energy events, such as matrix cracks, appear as burst emissions. Although researchers have shown the relation between damage types and AE signals, it is a rather involved process to do. Therefore, the AE technique is mainly applied in order to see when the material begins to fail or to see how serious the state of damage has become [4], [10].

The frequency spectrum where the AE signals lie is large, between 10 – 15000 kHz, although up to 90% of the signals are under 550 kHz [11]. Events yield different frequencies according to their type [12], [13]. Damage frequencies are not the only thing that separates the different types as they have also been shown to have variable amplitude. Research has shown that fiber breakage provides the most significant amplitude [14].

Due to the high sampling rate needed to measure AE frequencies, even the shortest signals are very demanding on computer memory; therefore it has become common to store only certain variables that are intended to describe the main features of the signal. From those features the status of the material is then analyzed [4].

In relation to the post-processing of AE signals, four main categories are highly relevant: AE activity analysis, AE parameter analysis, AE frequency analysis and AE modal analysis [1].

In AE analyzing, despite which category, it is important to be aware that the relative positioning of the sound source and sensor has an impact on the outcome. Factors such as decreased energy, dispersion and reflections inside the material change the signal on its way to the sensor. This has often been a source of misinterpretation when damages are being positioned in a material using AE analysis [6], [15].

TESTING PROCEDURE AND EQUIPMENT

The following describes the testing procedure. A numbered foot is fastened in the stiffness testing machine. The machine is a MTS QTEST/10LP³ and comes with a computer program called TestWorks QT, Version 2.03. First, the natural frequency test is carried out. An acceleration transducer from Brüel & Kjær⁴, Type 4367, is fastened between the two boltholes in the slot on the front part of the sole (see Fig. 2 on the right). The transducer is connected to a PC through a Brüel & Kjær Nexus conditional amplifier, Type 2692. To start an impulse, the front most part of the toe is bent as far as possible, by hand. When it is released, an impulse vibrates through the foot. The transducer picks up the time-dependant signal. The signal is low pass filtered at 1000 Hz and sampled at 2500 Hz using MATLAB⁵ and can be analyzed using Fast-Fourier transforms.

Fig. 2: Left: A specimen placed in the stiffness testing machine with an AE transducer attached, Right: A top view of a foot, showing the slot and boltholes under the sole.

The AE- and stiffness measurements are executed simultaneously. The transducer used for the AE measurement is an SE9125-MI AE transducer with an internal amplifier from Deci Inc⁶. The frequency response range for the amplifiers is between 20 kHz - 1.5 MHz; the amplification is 20 dB. The signal is amplified in the transducer to get a better signal to noise ratio (SNR) before transmitting it. Because all cables and equipment add some noise to the signal, it is important to get a good SNR from the transducer. The transducer is connected to a custom-built power adaptor (+15 Volt DC), required for powering the internal amplifier. The power is transmitted to the transducer using the same cable used for outputting the signal from the transducer. The output from the power adaptor is put into a Hope Electronics Wide Band Amplifier A100 where the signal is amplified by another 20 dB.

Before inputting the signal into the A/D converter, strong low frequency components have to be removed. There is much activity in low frequencies; removing them allows for more magnification of the high frequencies before digitizing. The signal is therefore put into a Krohn-Hite 3202 two channel low/high pass filter, where it is high pass filtered, using a fourth-order Butterworth filter where the cutoff frequency is set at 25 kHz. The A/D converter used is a PCI-6250 from National Instruments⁷.

The membrane of the transducer is lubricated with silicon oil and fastened with a plastic clamp on the lowest part of the heel. That position was confirmed to be the best, since bending during the stiffness testing is at its minimum in this position and therefore the contact area is at its closest for a constant measure throughout. The time of the AE signal acquisition

³ www.mts.com

⁴ www.bksv.com

⁵ www.mathworks.com

⁶ www.deci.com

⁷ www.ni.com

reaches over both loading (the actual stiffness testing) and also unloading of the specimen. The whole process' duration is 16.25 seconds. The spectrum of the signal was limited up to 200 kHz; a 400 kHz sampling rate yielded 6,500,000 data samples.

POST-PROCESSING AND RESULTS

Acoustic Emission

Until now, 96 specimens have given usable measurements of AE signals. Of the 96, 16 were specially made defected. In 8 specimens, defects were specially installed by not heating the layers for sufficient adhesiveness causing visible air gaps. The other 8 had large and visible delaminations as a result of tape strips put in between some of the layers in the panel. Other specimens were made as usual and therefore it was not known beforehand if they were faulty or not.

One defect of the AE measurement is a DC offset. Before the analyzing of the AE signals started, they were high-pass filtered to eliminate DC. The filtering was executed with the assistance of a digital elliptical filter in the MATLAB. Signals below 40 kHz were filtered out; since by inspection, it was seen that activity below that frequency was mainly noise.

Fig. 3: Typical acoustic emission during stiffness testing for the specimens tested.

Fig. 3 illustrates the behavior of most of the specimens; most of the activity is concentrated around the middle of the signal, just as the load is at its turning point.

When analyzing the signal, we are seeking outstanding features that might divide the group into different categories which means that one measurement alone is not meant to give much information; but all of them taken collectively would.

The first view taken on the AE signal is a parameter analysis. Numerical features such as peak count, length of event and energy of event are extracted from the signal. In order to separate the noise of the measurement from true events, only the part of the signal that is larger than 4 standard deviations of the noise is used, similar to what was suggested by Rippengill et al. [16]. The magnitude of the factors obtained should yield the amount of activity in the specimens, which could relate to the state of their viability.

In Fig. 4, the feet with air gaps are numbered 81-88 and the ones with delaminations are numbered. 89-96. The energy of events is by far the highest for specimen no. 48 but some other specimens with numbers ranging between 35 to 55 also show considerably higher energy. For duration or peak count, the difference between specimens is not as obvious, although there are three groups that outrank others, specifically those around 30, 50 and the ones with the installed delaminations.

Fig. 4: The values of three different parameters processed from AE signals for 96 specimens. Upper left: Energy, Upper right: Duration, Bottom: Peak count.

Another approach is relevant. During bending the maximum bending stress area moves along the specimen. It could be assumed that it is most likely that an activity originates from the area under the most stress each time. The timing of the activity can therefore be related to certain positions in the specimen. Therefore it seems appropriate to group the specimens that show damages at similar times.

Fig. 5: Energy over three different time periods for 96 specimens. The plot to the upper left is for the first 6 seconds, the upper right plot covers the 6.-10. second and the one in the bottom is for the remaining time up to 16.25 seconds.

The three plots in Fig. 5 provide an activity spread over time for all of the samples. Only activities large enough to reach more than 4 standard deviations in size were added together. Most activity is around the center of the time (upper right plot), which is almost the same as the plot for the whole period shown in Fig. 4. For all three periods there are specimens that show significantly more activity than others, but in no case does that involve the specimens known to be defected (the last 16).

The last inspection of the AE signal was a frequency analysis. All the specimens showed a very similar power spectrum from the FFT analysis. Few specific frequencies were emphasized in the same relative proportions; most similarity could be seen between specimens originating from the same panel. Specimens numbered 35-50 and also the delaminated specimens, 89-96, showed as abnormal where the frequency around 55 kHz was unusually small.

Fig. 6: Left: A typical FFT of an AE signal. Right: An exception in the FFT of the AE signals.

Natural Frequencies and Stiffness

The natural frequency spectrums usually have only one distinct peak where frequency depends on the stiffness of the specimen. For our specimens the frequency of this peak is around 150 Hz. Some spectrums show small peaks around 500 and 1000 Hz, but this is not connected with specimens known to be defected. In this analysis, even the highest frequency of the spectrum has such a large wavelength that defects must be considerable in order to show influence.

Fig. 7: The two main types of natural frequency spectrums obtained, results for two different specimens.

From the stiffness measurements, 102 valid stiffness curves were retrieved. 15 curves came from the specially made defected specimens (no. 81-96, leaving out the failed no. 93), all the others were made regularly but the testing for no. 33-41 did not give usable results.

As a result of manufacturing variations, all specimens do not have the same stiffness. In order to compare the stiffness curves of the specimens, they all had to be normalized, by dividing the load values of each curve by their peak load value. Thus each curve obtained load values ranging between 0 and 1.

Fig. 8: Left: A typical stiffness curve (not normalized). Right: Values of the area under the normalized stiffness curves. The gaps in the plot take the place of unsuccessful measurements.

It can be seen in the stiffness curves how the incline changes as the point of loading moves from the thin toe to the thicker zone around the ankle of the foot. We were interested to see if any of the specimens had to be loaded more on the way to their peak load than the rest. To analyze this, the area under the normalized stiffness curves was computed and compared but results did not provide specific indications of the defected specimens. At such an early stage in the loading of the specimens used, defects can even enhance the stiffness on account of stress concentration.

Fatigue Testing

The experiment goal was to find faulty specimens. It was not known if a certain specimen was damaged, with the exception of the ones deliberately prepared defective or if the specimens had superficial flaws. Fatigue testing can determine the quality of a specimen. Fatigue testing is time intensive and our facility only allowed for testing one specimen at a time; therefore a limited number of specimens could be tested.

Fig. 9: Results from fatigue testing of selected specimens.

Fig. 9 shows that the two specimens tested, that were specially damaged (81 with air gaps and 89 with delaminations), have the shortest endurance. A lack of strength is also seen for specimens 29 and 49 while specimens 72 and 73 held up to testing much longer than the others.

Fig. 10 shows that duration and peak count of AE events are capable of indicating the quality of the specimens. High values of these parameters can reveal low quality and vice versa. Of the 8 specimens examined, the intentionally damaged (far left on both plots in Fig. 10) are the ones who contradict this the most. The specimen tested from the delaminated panel was a special one; it was the only one from that panel that did not show high values for the two parameters. All the others in the panel were expected to have shown the tendency suggested.

Fig. 10: The connection between endurance in fatigue testing and parameters duration and peak count of the AE signal.

CONCLUSIONS

Of the three methods tested in the purpose of assessing the quality of CFRP prosthetic feet, one turned out to be effective: AE signal analysis. The features duration and peak count of AE events proved helpful for recognizing defective specimens. Comparison to fatigue testing for the specimens in question showed a correlation between the two parameters and the quality of the specimen. Analyzing stiffness and natural frequency response did not yield significant findings.

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